

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF RESIDUAL STRESSES IN DUCTILE IRON CASTING

Okechukwu Victor Chibuikem¹, Obinwa Yusuf², and Nwanguma Samuel³

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Federal University of
Technology Owerri (FUTO)

ABSTRACT

Residual stresses are a common occurrence in most manufacturing and fabrication processes, and they can persist even after all external loads have been removed. Despite extensive studies to determine the magnitude and distribution of residual stresses during different manufacturing processes, there is still much work to be done to comprehend their formation during the casting process. Although residual stresses are relatively small in magnitude, they can result in crack formation and subsequent failure in later phases of component usage, making it essential to understand their impact on the performance and durability of the final product. In this study, the test subject (a ductile iron gully grating) whose CAD model is provided by Nigerian Foundries Limited and modelled in SolidWorks 3D CAD. The residual stresses developed in the bracket after the casting process are analyzed using SIMULIA ABAQUS V6.14.5 software. The analysis is conducted through finite element simulations in an uncoupled thermal and structural environment. The analysis is carried out to identify the areas of residual stress present on the casting. The results of this analysis are then used to undertake geometrical topology optimization of the cast part for minimum or no residual stresses. The resulting shape has been shown to have much lesser and more evenly distributed residual stresses, reduction in weight for same load capacity, and increased fatigue strength, thereby improving the performance and durability of the final product.

Keywords: Residual stresses, topology optimization, Finite element analysis (FEA).

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of study

Casting is a manufacturing process in which a liquid material is usually poured into a mold that contains a cavity of the desired shape and then allowed to solidify. The solidified part is also known as the casting, which is ejected or broken from the mold to complete the process. [1] There are several types of metal casting processes including sand casting, which is the most extensively and widely used types of metal casting process. This is a destructive mold-permanent pattern casting process. The sand casting process involves the use of a furnace, metal, pattern, and sand mold. Die casting involves forcing molten metal into a reusable steel mold under high pressure. This method can produce parts with excellent dimensional accuracy and surface finish. It is typically used for high volume production runs of small to medium-sized parts. Investment casting, also known as lost-wax casting, involves creating a wax pattern which is coated in ceramic material to create a mold. The wax is then melted out of the mold and molten metal is poured into the cavity. This method produces parts with high accuracy and good surface finish. However, for all these casting and other manufacturing processes, there is induced residual stresses on the surface of the component produced. These residual stresses can be either beneficial or in some cases detrimental to the performance of the component in question said J.E. Wyatt et al. [2]

Residual stresses arise during the solidification process as a result of temperature variations between different areas of the casting. They can also occur due to mechanical constraints placed on the metal by the mold as it shrinks, or due to volumetric changes and transformation plasticity that occur during solid state phase transformation according to Chandra. When a casting has a complex geometry, it will have more internal sections which take longer to cool. Therefore, these sections will initially experience compressive loading. As the casting contracts within the already cold outer part, these sections will change to tensile loading. This change increases the magnitude of tensile residual stresses produced during cooling of the cast. Since the residual stresses can either increase or decrease the fatigue life of a component, it is important to consider their effects during design and manufacturing, an interest on its consideration during the design process has grown in the foundry industry.

1.2 Statement of problem

Residual stresses are a major concern in casted parts as they can significantly reduce the mechanical properties and performance of the parts. Despite advances in casting technology and process optimization, residual stresses still remain a problem. Therefore, there is a need to develop more effective methods to simulate and predict the formation of residual stresses in castings and to identify optimal designs and parameters that can reduce such stresses. This study aims to investigate the formation of residual stresses in castings using the finite element analysis and to develop a topology optimization framework to minimize such stresses by optimizing the casting design and process parameters. The proposed study will contribute to a better understanding of the factors that influence residual stresses in castings and provide insights into the use of topology optimization as a practical approach to improve the quality and reliability of casted parts.

1.3 Objectives of study

The aim of this paper is the finite element analysis of residual stresses in ductile iron casting

Other specific objectives are;

- i. To utilize topology optimization technique to design a better part that alleviates or reduces said residual stresses.
- ii. To visually compare results of the optimized casting geometry to the original one

1.4 Significance of study

The significance of this study is that it highlights the importance of reducing or alleviating residual stresses in ductile iron castings. This is crucial to prevent the formation of cracks and creeps in later stages of the product life-cycle, which ultimately reduces the fatigue life of the parts. By implementing the methods used in this study, manufacturers in the casting industry will be able to produce better and longer-lasting parts.

Moreover, the study also provides valuable insights into how residual stresses can be controlled and allowed in areas where they are necessary for the proper functioning of the product. This information will be instrumental in helping manufacturers strike a balance between minimizing residual stresses and maintaining the required level of strength and durability in their parts. Ultimately, this study has the potential to significantly improve the quality and longevity of ductile iron castings, benefiting both manufacturers and end-users alike.

1.5 Justification of study

- i. Manufacturers in the casting industry can learn from this research to produce better products.
- ii. There is limited research in this field and this study can form a framework for more detailed in-depth for upcoming researchers.

1.6 Scope of study

This study will analyze the residual stress concentrations of a casted ductile iron gully grating. The grating geometry will be modified based on analysis results in order to alleviate or reduce any residual stresses on the part. A comparison will then be made between the new optimized and the original casting to visualize the differences.

This study is only concerned with the reduction of residual stresses considering only the design or geometric factor. The residual stresses accrued on the part due to the casting process, heat treatment and possibly machining are not considered in this study. Hence, this study provides a means to analyze and take into consideration residual stresses of a part to be casted from the design stage.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Residual Stresses

Residual stresses, also referred to as trapped or locked stresses, are non-homogeneous and self-balanced stresses that are generated during various manufacturing processes of engineering components. What makes these stresses unique is that they exist within solid materials even in the absence of external mechanical or thermal loads. In other words, these are specific stresses that remain within a material after the manufacturing stage, when there is neither external force nor thermal gradient applied. [1]-[3] In castings, residual stresses can develop during the solidification process due to temperature variations or mechanical constraints.

The following are the sources of residual stresses in castings

1. Strain caused by viscoelastic flow and temperature gradients

This occurs during the cooling and solidification process. When the melted metal in a casting process cools down and solidifies, residual stresses arise from the strain caused by viscoelastic flow and temperature gradients. This means that as the metal cools and solidifies, it undergoes changes in its physical properties such as volume and shape. These changes can cause internal stresses within the material due to the non-uniform expansion and contraction rates from point to point within castings. The temperature gradients can also cause uneven cooling rates which can lead to the development of residual stresses.

Figure 1: Stress caused by viscoelastic flow

- Heat treatment: A significant amount of residual stresses can be developed in aluminum castings during heat treatment. For example, cast aluminum alloys are usually subject to a T6 heat treatment which includes a solution treatment at a relatively high temperature, quench in a cold medium such as water, then age hardening at an intermediate temperature. This process can develop residual stresses in the material. [2]

Figure 2: Stress caused by temperature gradient

- Macroscopic residual stresses: These types of residual stresses can arise from various manufacturing processes such as heat treatment, machining, secondary processing and assembly. These processes can cause changes in the material's physical properties which can lead to the development of residual stresses.

Figure 3: Representation of macroscopic residual stresses

- Microstructural stresses: These types of residual stresses often result from the CTE (coefficient of thermal expansion) mismatch between phases and constituents or from

phase transformations. This means that when different parts of the material expand or contract at different rates due to changes in temperature or phase transformations, it can cause internal stresses within the material.

2.2 Previous studies

This work deals extensively with the simulation of residual stresses. Hence of a lot of literature have been studied to model the optimum finite element (FE) problem, the development of thermal stresses and predict the hot tearing and residual stresses in shaped casting.

Si Young Kwak et al [3] investigated the effect of the residual stresses generated during the heat treatment process on yielding behavior of a constant stress beam using numerical analysis and experimental study.

The constant stress specimen of SUS304 was heat-treated in cooling water after heating and maintaining for 2 h at 950 °C to generate residual stress, and then the residual stress was measured using ESPI. The external bending stress was measured using ESPI again after applying a load of 300 kgf (2.8 mm) on the specimen.

Height ratio and dimensionless height are defined by the equation below

$$\text{Height ratio} = th/t_0$$

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC 4: Residual stresses generated on a constant stress beam

Ragab et al. [4] have used a coupled thermo-mechanical finite element model to simulate the die casting process. The simulation models show the effect of thermal and mechanical interaction between the casting and the die. It also includes the temperature dependent material properties of the casting.

Metzget et al. [5] have studied a method to efficiently predict residual stresses in foundry product by FEM.

Vijayaram et al. [6] have studied casting solidification simulation process which was used to identify the defective locations in the castings from the generated time–temperature contours.

Afazov et al. [7] studied FE prediction of residual stresses of investment casting in a bottom core vane under equiaxed cooling and presented an investment casting simulation of the same to find the residual stresses.

Xue et al. [8] did the numerical simulation of casting thermal stresses based on finite difference stress problems during solidification process.

Koric et al. [9] applied a three-dimensional transient explicit finite-element method to simulate the coupled and highly-nonlinear thermomechanical phenomenon that occurs during steel solidification in continuous casting of thin slabs in a funnel mold.

method using a three-dimensional code which was developed for solving thermal elastoplastic

Afazov et al. [10] presented a finite element simulation of an investment casting of a high pressure turbine blade under directional cooling.

2.2.1 Topology optimization

Topology optimization is a mathematical method that optimizes material layout within a given design space, for a given set of loads, boundary conditions and constraints with the goal of maximizing the performance of the system [11]. It has been used to reduce residual stresses in casting by optimizing the geometry of the cast part for minimum residual stresses [12].

In one study, the residual stresses developed in a shifter during the casting process were first determined by finite element analysis. The results showed the areas of maximum residual stress. This was followed by the geometrical optimization of the cast part for minimum residual stresses. The resulting shape gave lesser and more evenly distributed residual stresses. Crack compliance method was used to experimentally determine the residual stresses in the modified cast part. The results obtained from the measurements were verified by the finite element analysis findings [13].

There are numerous techniques to perform topology optimization, such as the homogenization-based method, the density-based method, the evolutionary method, and the boundary variation method¹. Some of the most popular methods are the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) technique and the Evolutionary Structural Optimization (ESO) technique. [14] [15].

Homogenization-based method: The homogenization method for topology optimization is a mathematical tool that can be used to optimize material layout within a given design space for a given set of loads, boundary conditions and constraints with the goal of maximizing the performance of the system

The goal of this method is to review the necessary mathematical tools of homogenization theory and apply them to topology optimization of mechanical structures. The ultimate application targeted by this method is the topology optimization of structures built with lattice materials [16]. The homogenization-based method for topology optimization has the advantage of being able to provide the optimal design with theoretical bounds on structural efficiency. It can also be used to optimize structures built with lattice materials. However, this method has limited computational efficiency as it can be quite cumbersome to evaluate and determine the complex geometric parameters of optimal microstructures¹. Additionally, the use of mathematical programming methods for realistic topology optimization problems can be somewhat impractical, as they usually require hundreds of finite elements, and therefore hundreds of design variables.

Solid Isotropic Material with penalization (SIMP) technique: The Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) method is a popular mathematical method for topology optimization. It was initially proposed by Bendsoe and Kikuchi (1988) and Rozvany and Zhou (1992)¹. The SIMP method predicts an optimal material distribution within a given

design space, for given load cases, boundary conditions, manufacturing constraints, and performance requirements.

According to Bendsoe (1989), "shape optimization in its most general setting should consist of a determination for every point in space whether there is material in that point or not"¹. The traditional approach to topology optimization is the discretization of a domain into a grid of finite elements called isotropic solid microstructures. Each element is either filled with material for regions that require material or emptied of material for regions where you can remove material (representing voids).

The introduction of a continuous relative density distribution function avoids the binary, on-off nature of the problem. For each element, the assigned relative density can vary between a minimum value (ρ_{min}) and 1, which allows the assignment of intermediate densities for elements (characterized as porous elements). ρ_{min} is the minimum allowable relative density value for empty elements that are greater than zero. This density value ensures the numerical stability of the finite element analysis. [17]

The SIMP (Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization) method has several advantages. It is versatile, converges well and is easy to implement¹. It has become generally accepted as a topology optimization technique with overwhelming advantages

However, one limitation of the SIMP method is that the resulting topologies can include areas of intermediate densities ("gray areas"), which have no physical meaning¹. This can be overcome by integrating other methods with SIMP to obtain topologies that are stiffer and have fewer gray areas than those obtained only with SIMP. [18]

The Evolutionary Structural Optimization (ESO) method was introduced by Xie and Steven in 1993 to overcome structural optimization problems by improving and optimizing the design of structures [19]. The ESO method evolves a structure from the full design domain towards an optimum by gradually removing inefficient material.

One advantage of the ESO method is that it is based on a simple concept and can be used to obtain a fully stressed structure with an updated topology. However, one limitation of the ESO method is that it may not always result in a completely satisfactory topology, as it can include areas of intermediate densities ("gray areas"), which have no physical meaning. [20].

The finite element method (FEM) is the most common and practical technique for topology optimization, as it breaks the design into parts and tests each finite element for rigidity, compliance, and redundant material [21].

2.3 Residual stress experimental techniques:

Experimental techniques for assessing residual stresses can be divided into three main groups based on the measurement depth and level of material removed: destructive, semi-destructive, and non-destructive. Non-destructive methods are relatively more expensive but provide accurate results, primarily measuring residual stresses close to the surface layer, excluding neutron and synchrotron methods. More information on non-destructive methods can be found in reference [22].

On the other hand, destructive and semi-destructive techniques, also known as mechanical techniques, are cost-effective and do not require high-tech equipment. These methods evaluate residual stresses through the depth of specimens by incrementally removing material and simultaneously determining deformations, traditionally using strain gauges or modernly utilizing non-contacting optical methods such as Digital Image Correlation (DIC) or Moiré Interferometry, as described in reference [23]. Residual stresses are then found by using an integral-form equation that relates measured strains to residual stresses. A detailed explanation of various optical methods for recording deformations in stress-relief techniques is presented in reference [24].

2.3.1 Contour Method

To measure the longitudinal residual stress, the contour method, first proposed by Prime in 2000 is used [25]. This method shows the residual stress distribution over the entire section of the assembly, and its results are often compared with those from the non-destructive neutron diffraction measurements [26]-[29]. The conventional contour method can only measure one residual stress component across the part's cross-section. Pagliaro et al. introduced a new approach to contour measurement of residual stresses in 2010 [30], which involved making multiple cuts to measure multiple residual stress components (Fig. 3). This new technique was simpler to apply than the multi-axial contour method and did not need an extruded cross-section. However, it had the drawback of measuring different stress components on different cross-sections of the part.

2.3.2 Slitting Method

The slitting method or crack compliance method is a destructive method that has evolved since its debut in 1986. It involves cutting a slot gradually through the specimens' depth (x-direction in (Fig. 4) and measuring the resulting deformations to estimate residual stresses. Fig. 4 shows a slot with depth and width of 'a' and 'w', respectively, and a specimen with dimensions 't', 'L' and 'B'. 'l' represents the strain gauge length. The slitting technique can be useful for components made by layer deposition methods, such as filament winding, laser cladding, and rapid prototyping [32]. Recently, a modified slitting method, called the slotting method, has successfully measured residual stresses in bone structures, especially through-depth stresses in layers near the surface of bovine femurs [33].

Figure 6: Diagrammatic representation of Slitting method. Adapted with permission from reference [31]. Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

2.3.3 Hole drilling Method

One common way to measure the residual stresses in specimens through their depth is hole drilling, which has different types such as “central or blind hole drilling” and “incremental or deep hole drilling” [34]–[36]. The hole drilling technique has an ASTM Standard Test Method E837 that was introduced in 1981. This method is similar to the slitting method in many ways, but it only damages the drilled area, so it is a semi-destructive technique. This method may not measure stresses as deep as the slitting method, but it is easier to apply and has a standardized testing procedure, which makes it more preferable than other methods [37] [38]. Fig. 5 shows a schematic of clockwise strain gauge rosettes in this method. The positive x-direction is along the axis of gauge 1, the negative y-direction is along the axis of gauge 3, and a circular hole is drilled at the center of that.

ASTM standard 45° strain gauge rosette used for residual stress measurement
(Courtesy: Measurements Group)

$$\sigma_{\max}, \sigma_{\min} = \frac{\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3}{4\bar{A}} \pm \frac{\sqrt{(\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_1 - 2\varepsilon_3)^2}}{4\bar{B}}$$

Equation 1

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \arctan \left[\frac{\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_1 - 2\varepsilon_3}{\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1} \right] \text{ where:}$$

Equation 2

$\sigma_{\max}, \sigma_{\min}$ - Maximum and minimum principal stresses (Pa);

$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$ - Measured strains at gauges 1, 2 and 3;

\bar{A} and \bar{B} - Constants (material and rosette dependant);

β - Angle between the measured principal stress and gauge 1. [ASTM E837 - 95, 1997]

2.3.4 Ring core Method

The ring core method is a semi-destructive technique that was introduced in 1951 and patented in 1988. It was developed to overcome some practical limitations of the hole drilling method. It involves milling a small circular groove around the point of interest and measuring the residual stress from the surface deformations of the core. Unlike the hole-drilling method, which removes material from the center and measures strains on the outside, the ring-core method removes material from the outside and measures strains on the inside. The advantage of this method is that it does not destroy the specimen completely and it can be repeated (by taking out the core and re-installing the strain gauge rosette). It can also measure residual stress at a much deeper depth than other methods and it is more sensitive in strain measurement [39].

2.3.5 XRD (X-Ray diffraction) Method

XRD is a non-destructive method that measures the in-situ strains in a material by using the crystalline planes as strain gauges. This method uses the classical theory of elasticity and the Bragg's law equation to relate the strains and stresses [40] – [42]. The diffracted beams form

circular intensity rings called Debye rings, which are recorded by a two-dimensional detector perpendicular to the incident beam (Fig. 7). The stress changes the inter-planar distance and distorts the Debye rings at the detector. The amount of distortion in the direction of stress gives a good estimate of the lattice strain. Fig. 7 shows the schematic of strain measurement in the XRD method

Figure 8: a) Schematic of the XRD experiment, b) Two-dimensional diffraction pattern recorded in the detector. The intensity rings present diffractions from different lattice planes of the crystal. Adapted with permission from reference [43]. Copyright 2011, Tay

2.3.6 Ultrasonic Method

The Ultrasound method is a non-destructive technique that measures the stress through the thickness of a material. The speed of ultrasound waves in a material changes with the residual stress level, direction and sign. By measuring the difference in time of flight of an ultrasound wave in stressed and unstressed regions, the residual stress can be calculated. However, the ultrasound waves are also affected by microstructural and temperature variations [44] [45]. The difference in time of flight, Δt , depends on four effective parameters:

$$\Delta t = \Delta t_{AS} + \Delta t_{RS} + \Delta t_T + \Delta t_M \quad (2.1)$$

Where Δt_{AS} is the effect of applied stress changes, Δt_{RS} is the effect of residual stress changes, Δt_T is the effect of temperature changes and Δt_M is the effect of microstructure

changes. Accounting for the microstructural variations in this equation is often difficult. The Ultrasound method has some benefits, such as being non-destructive and suitable for a wide range of materials. However, it also has some drawbacks: it is sensitive to microstructural changes; it requires a high-quality surface finish and it cannot be used in complex-shaped structures.

2.4 Review of experimental validation of residual stresses:

A.A Keste et al [13] validated their FEA model by using crack compliance method, also known as incremental slitting method. It is a fracture mechanics based approach. A detailed literature survey is done before selecting this method though various other residual stress measurement techniques are available. This method involves the determination of a residual stress by successive extension of a slot and measurement of the resulting strains or displacements. It is a destructive technique but has increased spatial resolution for residual stresses and increased sensitivity to low stresses. The basic principle of this technique is that the slit will be cut incrementally with depth (x-direction) and simultaneously the residual stresses will release on the plane normal to the slit (y-z). Strain gauges mounted on this plane will measure the strain change caused by this stress release after every increment

Figure 9: Schematic of A.A Keste's experimental setup

B. Venu et al measured their FEA model using the sectioning method. The elongation (length difference in %) is measured using a strain gauge. Using only one gauge is not sufficient; several gauges are required in order to accumulate accurate data.

To measure elongation, the strain gauge is attached to the surface of the test piece using an appropriate adhesive that completely covers the thin copper wiring to minimize errors. The gauge setup is simple and involves a Wheatstone bridge circuit, as shown in Figure 3.7, to calculate the resistance in the strain gauge. R-gauge, which has an unknown resistivity, can be determined by knowing all the other resistances in the circuit. The unknown resistivity changes with the strain of the section and can thus be used to measure strain. Figure 3.7 illustrates the Wheatstone bridge circuit and how the gauge is incorporated.

Si Young Kwak et al [3] measured the residual stresses generated during quenching heat treatment of a constant stress beam in advance by using the ESPI (Electronic Speckle-Pattern Interferometry) equipment.

*Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC 10: Si Young Kwak's experimental setup*

ESPI (Electronic Speckle Pattern Interferometry) is a non-contact measurement apparatus used for measuring the amount of displacement of the entire area for a strain analysis. ESPI employs coherent laser illumination on the specimen and monitors the change in intensity pattern with a CDD camera. It provides displacement vector information of the entire area when the laser beam is irradiated on the specimen from different directions. The

displacement fields are numerically differentiated in order to obtain strain maps. The measurement of deformation is scaled by the wavelength λ of the laser beam [46]

Table 1: The height ratios of the measuring holes and measured stresses

SYMBOL	Before applying load		While applying load	
	Height ratio	Measured Stress	Height ratio	Measured Stress
A1	-0.38	-286	0.38	-186
A2	-0.34	-199	0.29	-99
A3	-0.43	-271	0.48	-205
A4	-0.58	-323	0.62	-290
B1	0.62	-321	-0.62	-330
B2	0.48	-307	-0.53	-325
B3	0.82	-358	-0.86	-378

Figure 11: Graph of Si Young Kwak's results

Brown et al. [47] compared the results of residual stress measurement in an electron-beam welded uranium cylinder via the contour and neutron diffraction methods. The results indicated that neutron diffraction assesses stresses approximately 50 MPa lower than the contour method. Possible sources of this error were discussed in this paper in detail. The process. It is therefore seen that many studies associated with welding operations have employed the contour method for measuring residual stresses.

2.3 PROCESSES INVOLVED

2.3.1 Casting process

The oldest known casting process, sand casting can be traced back to earlier than 1000 B.C. [48]. While there have been significant advances in process controls, material options, tolerance capabilities, and size ranges, the basic principle remains the same. A cavity is created in the desired shape and molten metal is poured into it to form the casting. This method is still widely used today due to its ability to produce elaborate parts.

Sand casting is the most versatile metal casting method, and probably the most widely used, due to centuries of development. The choice of metalworking process for manufacturing a product is determined by design requirements such as shaping and dimensional needs, piece and tooling cost, quantity needed, and feasibility of manufacturing.

While sand casting is capable of producing shaped parts of nearly any design, including very large parts and those with internal passageways, there may be more optimal casting or metalworking processes for specific products based on:

- Needed tolerances

- Design intricacy
- Volume
- Tooling availability
- Lead time

Producing The Pattern – Desired Product

- The process utilizes a reusable pattern with the same details as the desired finished part. There is an allowance for thermal contraction or shrink.

B. Producing The Pattern – Gates and Risers: The Metal Delivery System

- The pattern produced in step “A” also includes the metal pathways that will feed the desired cast product design with appropriate gating and risers. This drives the inevitable thermal contraction to acceptable areas (someplace other than the actual desired finished product), and manages the metal flow and needed gas venting.
- Patterns are made of many different materials such as wood, metal, synthetics, expandable polystyrene (EPS), and others depending on needed volume and tolerance.

C. Creating The Mold

- A refractory material which is stable at high temperature (sand, in our example) is formed around the pattern. The material must be strong enough to hold the weight of the molten metal during casting and resistant to reaction with the metal, yet brittle enough to be readily broken away from the solidified metal after the casting cools.
- There are a variety of sand materials that can be used to make the mold. The sand typically includes other materials like clay or some chemical bonding agent to strengthen it so that it will stand up to the pouring process.
- Alternatively, the mold may be created by machining the desired shaped cavity directly into a block of sand. The technique is widely used during product development because design changes may be managed and implemented quickly, or

for parts with infrequent usage to avoid the storage or maintenance of a physical pattern.

- The mold is typically produced in two pieces, the top half or “cope” and the bottom half or “drag”. Once the sand has set (using the traditional/non-machined process), the halves are separated, and the pattern removed. A refractory coating is added to provide a better surface finish and protect the mold from the turbulence of the poured metal. The halves are placed back together, leaving a cavity in the shape of the pattern.
- The mold may also include cores, a method that is used to produce desired internal passageways in the final product.

D. Pouring The Metal into The Mold

- Molten metal is poured directly into the static mold. It fills the cavity that defines both the finished part and risers. The risers feed the casting with an available supply of liquid metal. As they are designed to cool and solidify last, they shrink, and potential void, is concentrated in the riser rather than in the desired part.
- There are several variations of “tilt pouring”. It is a process designed to allow metal to flow more smoothly into the casting, eliminating turbulence. Less turbulence can help prevent the creation of oxides and casting defects.
- Virtually any alloy can be produced using this process. For those materials particularly reactive with oxygen, a procedure such as argon shielding may be employed to keep air away from the molten metal.

E. Shakeout

- The casting, including both the desired part and the additional metal needed to create it, solidifies and cools. The sand is broken away in a shakeout process.
- Much of the sand used to create the mold is captured, reconditioned, and reused.

F. Final Operations

- The gates, runners, and risers are cut from the casting, and if necessary, final post-processing sandblasting, grinding, etc., are performed to finish the casting dimensionally. Sand castings often require at least some additional machining to reach final dimensions or tolerances.
- Parts may be heat-treated to improve dimensional stability or properties.
- Non-destructive testing may also be performed. That could include fluorescent penetrant, magnetic particle, radiographic, or other inspections. Final dimensional inspections, alloy test results, and NDT are verified prior to shipment.

2.3.2 Casting theory

2.3.2.1 Pattern making

Shrinkage: to compensate for metal shrinkage during cooling from freezing to room temp

Shrinkage allowance = $\alpha L(T_f - T_0)$ expressed as per unit length for a given material α =
coeff. of thermal expansion, T_f = freezing temp T_0 = room temp

2.3.2.2 Melting

For a pure metal: total heat energy required, H = energy to raise temp of metal to melting point, T_m + heat of fusion, H_f + energy to raise temp of liquid metal to pouring temp, T_p

$$H = \rho V \left[c_s (T_m - T_0) + H_f + c_l (T_p - T_m) \right] \quad (2.2)$$

2.3.2.3 Pouring

Pouring rate: If poured too slow, a metal solidifies before complete mold filling and if poured too fast it can erode the surface of the mold hence resulting in a poor quality casting etc. Reynolds number: Laminar versus turbulent flow

ρ = density of liquid, V = mean flow velocity, D = tube diameter, η = dynamic viscosity of liquid.

$$Re = \frac{\rho V D}{\eta} \quad (2.3)$$

Most steels reach mildly turbulent flow conditions easily ($Re > 3500$)

Solidification time: The total solidification time is the time required for the casting to solidify after pouring.

$$t = \left[\frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{\rho_{casting} \Delta H_f}{T_m - T_0} \right)^2 \frac{1}{k_m \rho_m c_m} \right] \left(\frac{V}{A} \right)^2 \quad (2.4)$$

Subscripts

- m = mold
- ΔH_f = latent heat of solidification
- T_m = metal melting temperature

- T_0 = initial mold temperature

2.4 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.4.1 Heat transference

When a system is at a temperature different from its surroundings, the natural tendency is to achieve thermal equilibrium. This process is governed by the second law of thermodynamics, which dictates that thermal energy always flows from a higher temperature system to a lower temperature system. The transfer of thermal energy occurs through one or a combination of three basic heat transport mechanisms: conduction, convection, and radiation.

2.4.2 Conduction

This is the process of transferring heat through direct molecular communication, occurring by physical contact of the particles within a medium or between mediums. This phenomenon is observed in gases, liquids, and solids. Unlike convection or radiation, no bulk movement of the medium occurs in conduction. The governing equation for conduction is Fourier's law of heat conduction, which states that the heat flow per unit area is proportional to the normal temperature gradient, where the proportionality constant is the thermal conductivity.

$$q = -kA \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \quad (2.5)$$

where q is the heat flux perpendicular to a surface of area A , [W]; A is the surface area through which the heat flow occurs, [m²]; k is the thermal conductivity, [W/(mK)]; T is the temperature, [K] or [°C]; and x is the perpendicular distance to the surface travelled by the heat flux.

2.4.3 Convection

This refers to the heat transfer by mass motion of a fluid when the heated fluid moves away from the heat source. It combines conduction with the effect of a current of fluid that moves its heated particles to cooler areas and replaces them with cooler ones. The flow can be either due to buoyancy forces (natural convection) or due to artificially induced currents (forced convection). The governing equation for convection is derived from Newton's law of cooling and is typically expressed in the form of a heat transfer coefficient that relates the heat flux to the temperature gradient between the fluid and the surface.

$$q = -hA(T_{\infty} - T_s) \quad (2.6)$$

where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient [$W/(m^2 K)$]; T_{∞} is the temperature of the cooling fluid; and T_s is the temperature of the surface of the body.

2.4.4 Radiation

This is a form of energy that can be observed in the form of waves or moving subatomic particles. Thermal radiation, in particular, is of interest for its ability to transfer heat through the emission of electromagnetic waves from the surface of an object due to temperature differences, which carry energy away from the emitting object. The Stefan-Boltzmann law is the basic relationship governing radiation emitted from hot objects.

$$q = \varepsilon\sigma A(T_1^4 - T_2^4) \quad (2.7)$$

Where ε is the coefficient of emissivity (=1 for ideal radiator); σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant of proportionality ($5.669E-8$ [$W/(m^2K^4)$]); A is the radiating surface area; T_1 is the temperature of the radiator; and T_2 is the temperature of the surroundings.

2.4.5 Initial and Boundary conditions

To fully define a transient thermal problem, initial conditions and boundary conditions are necessary, along with the heat conduction equation. In the case of a steady-state problem, initial conditions are not required. The initial conditions represent the initial temperature distribution throughout the body. In casting processes, the initial condition is assumed to be

constant throughout the mold, and it is also assumed to be constant for the melt in the mold filling simulation, where the temperature is at a superheating temperature. For the solidification simulation, the initial condition is given by the temperature field immediately after filling. For simplicity, when there is no interest in the mold filling simulation, a constant temperature throughout the melt after filling can be assumed, and the superheating temperature of the melt can be used as the initial condition for the solidification simulation. Next, we introduce five types of boundary conditions relevant to the modeling of casting processes, along with their mathematical representation.

2.4.5.1 Perfectly insulated (adiabatic) boundary

An adiabatic boundary has no heat flux across.

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial n}(P, t) = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

where n is the outward pointing normal to the surface at point P . Another way to define this boundary condition is setting the heat transfer coefficient h to zero in Newton's law.

$$k \frac{\partial T}{\partial n}(P, t) = h(T_{\infty}(t) - T(P, t)) \quad (2.9)$$

where h is the convective heat transfer coefficient.

2.4.5.2 Radiation boundary condition

When a boundary surface receives heat by radiation, the following expression applies:

$$k \frac{\partial T}{\partial n}(P, t) = h_{rad}(T_{\infty}(t) - T(P, t)) \quad (2.10)$$

Where;

$$h_{rad} = \varepsilon\sigma(T_1^3 + T_1^2T_2 + T_1T_2^2 + T_2^3) \quad (2.11)$$

Which, for simplicity, assumes $h_{rad} = \text{constant}$. This is used when the time step of the analysis is so small that the temperatures may be assumed constant during the time step.

2.4.5.3 Internal boundary (two solids bodies in contact) condition

Next, five types of boundary conditions relevant for the modeling of casting processes are introduced together with their mathematical representation: $T_1(P, t) = T_2(P, t)$

$$k_1 \frac{\partial T_1}{\partial n}(P, t) = k_2 \frac{\partial T_2}{\partial n}(P, t) \quad (2.12)$$

The subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the two bodies.

2.4.6 THE HEAT CONDUCTION EQUATIONS

2.4.6.1 1-D transient (time dependent) heat conduction equation

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \dot{Q}_{gen}'' \quad (2.13)$$

Where \dot{Q}_{gen}'' is the internal generation of heat per unit time per unit volume present within the body

2.4.6.2 1-D steady-state heat conduction equation

Since the steady-state is independent of time, is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \dot{Q}_{gen}''' = 0 \quad (2.14)$$

2.4.6.2 The 3-D transient Heat Conduction Equation

For casting processes, it represents the basis of all heat conduction calculations. Is the general form of the heat conduction equation and is as follows:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) + \dot{Q}_{gen}^m \quad (2.15)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) \quad (2.16)$$

2.5 NUMERICAL SOLUTIONS

The numerical solution of partial differential equations aims to determine the value of the dependent variable at predefined nodal points within the calculation domain. The values of the dependent variable serve as the primary unknowns, and equation systems are developed for each nodal point in the domain. These equations, known as discretization equations, are written for every dependent variable at each nodal point. The calculation domain is divided into sub-domains, such as cells, elements, or control volumes. These sub-domains allow for a more precise identification of the dependent variable in smaller areas as a function of the values at the nodal points. This enables the application of different profiles to each sub-domain, which can be more suitable for the actual problem. The most commonly used numerical methods in casting simulations are the Finite Difference Method (FDM), the Finite Element Method (FEM), and the Finite Volume Method (FVM). While these methods differ in their profile assumptions and methods for deriving discretization equations, they share several commonalities, such as the need for a geometry definition, appropriate material data, definition of initial and boundary conditions, solvers of linear algebraic equations to perform calculations, and a postprocessor to present the results. [26]

2.5.1 Finite element method

1. The solution domain is divided into a grid of finite segments or elements.
2. The governing partial differential equations are solved for each element in mesh.
3. The elements are assembled together and the continuity requirements and equilibrium conditions are satisfied with adjacent elements.
4. A unique solution can be obtained to the whole system of linear algebraic equations once the boundary conditions are satisfied.
5. The solution matrix is populated with relatively few non-zero coefficients.
6. The FE method is suitable for the analysis of complex geometries and is not difficult to modify the element size in particular regions.

2.5.2 Finite difference method

1. The solution domain is divided into a grid of cells or elements
2. The derivatives in the governing partial differential equations are converted into finite difference equations.
3. These finite difference approximations are applied to each interior point so that the displacement of each node is a function of the displacements at the other nodes connected to it.
4. A unique solution can be obtained to the whole system of linear algebraic equations once the boundary conditions are satisfied.
5. The solution matrix is banded 6- The FD method is not suitable for very complex geometries and is difficult to change the element size in particular regions
6. The FD method is not as popular for stress analysis problems as for heat transfer and fluid flow problems. The approximation quality of the FE method is better, but it comes with a greatest computer calculation time price.

2.6 THE STRESS ANALYSIS

2.6.1 Residual stresses

Residual stresses are tensions or compressions that exist in the bulk of a material without applying an external load. In a casting process, while cooling, residual stresses are induced due to temperature gradients across the whole casting, mechanical constraints given by the mold during the shrinkage of the metal and volumetric change and transformation plasticity related to the solid-state phase transformation. Hence, residual stresses are a function of the shape of the casting and the cooling rate of the casting process. Compressive residual stresses are desirable in a component as they improve the fatigue life and reduce the stress corrosion cracking tendency since they also offer resistance to crack propagation.

2.6.2 Elasticity

Within a certain limit, when a load is applied, a component undergoes a deformation that is recovered when the load is released. This behavior of a material is known as elasticity and its limit is known as the elastic limit. The measure of the elastic behavior of a material is known as Young's modulus. This modulus is experimentally determined as the slope of the stress-strain curve obtained during tensile tests carried out on samples of a given material.

Elastic strain According to the Hook's law, within the elastic limit of a material the stress is proportional to the strain. This strain is known as elastic strain (ε^{el}) and is expressed as:

$$\varepsilon^{el} = \sigma/E \quad (2.17)$$

2.6.3 Thermal Strain

When a metal body is heated or cooled it expand or contract if it's free to deform. The amount of deformation that the body undergoes is then proportional to the rise or fall down of the temperature. This give place to the mathematical expression for the thermal strain:

$$\varepsilon^{th} = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \alpha(T)dT \quad (2.18)$$

This thermal deformation can be a contraction or an expansion and can result in deformation only or stresses only, if the body is free to contract or is totally constrained respectively or it can result in a combination of deformation and stresses which is the most common situation in reality for castings.

2.6.4 Plasticity

When a load applied to a material produces a deformation beyond the elastic limit, the material is said to be in the plastic region, where any deformation experienced is permanent. The transition from elastic to plastic behavior is called yield, and the stress that corresponds to this transition is called yield stress. At elevated temperatures, metals undergo such irreversible deformations, and in casting processes, which occur over a wide temperature range, this inelastic or plastic behavior becomes significant. In plasticity, it is not possible to define the stresses as functions of the strains in their total form (so Hooke's law, which is a total constitutive law, does not apply). Instead, it is possible to express the changes in stresses as changes in strains, which is known as an incremental constitutive law.

Ideal Plasticity is the simplest approximation to the inelastic behavior of a material. It assumes that the yield stress σ_y is constant, independent of the mechanical strain. The mechanical strain is equal to the elastic strain plus the plastic strain:

$$\varepsilon^{mech} = \varepsilon^{el} + \varepsilon^{pl} \quad (2.19)$$

And the total strain (the one see from outside the component) is the sum of the mechanical and the thermal strains and therefore the strain for the thermo-elastoplastic case:

$$\varepsilon^{total} = \varepsilon^{mech} + \varepsilon^{vh} = \varepsilon^{el} + \varepsilon^{pl} + \varepsilon^{th} \quad (2.20)$$

The differentiation between total strain and mechanical strain is important, particularly in defining ideal plasticity with respect to the latter. This is because, even if the total strain of a fully constrained component subjected to a thermal gradient is zero, the mechanical strain is not. It is the mechanical strain that should be used in the stress-strain plot.

2.6.5 Hardening

A better approximation to the real behavior of metallic materials is this concept of hardening because most of them instead of behave ideal plastically exhibit increasing stress with increasing plastic deformation, which the hardening approach assumes to have a linear relation. Hence is known as strain hardening or linear hardening.

Taking the temperature dependence into consideration, the two main dependences of yield stress for the plasticity in a casting process are: 1. Temperature 2. Plastic strain This can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_y(T, \epsilon^{pl}) \quad (2.21)$$

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC 14: Graph of Linear Hardening

2.7 THE STRESS ANALYSIS

Despite the significant progress that has been made in the study of residual stresses in castings and the use of topology optimization to reduce such stresses, there are still several gaps in knowledge that need to be addressed. One of the main challenges is the lack of accurate FEA models for predicting residual stresses in castings. Most of the current models rely on simplified assumptions and empirical correlations, which may not accurately capture the complex thermal and mechanical interactions that occur during the casting process. There is a need for more advanced and accurate FEA models that can account for the effects of non-uniform cooling rates, solidification shrinkage, and deformation due to thermal stresses. Another gap in knowledge is the limited application of topology optimization to more complex casting geometries, such as those with multiple cores and thin-walled sections. The optimization of such geometries requires more advanced optimization algorithms that can handle the high number of design variables and constraints involved. Additionally, there is a need for more research on how to integrate topology optimization with other design and manufacturing processes, such as additive manufacturing and post-processing techniques, to achieve a more seamless and efficient production process. Addressing these gaps in

knowledge will be crucial for advancing the field of residual stress reduction in castings and realizing the full potential of topology optimization for designing optimized casted parts.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials for the study

For this study, ductile iron is the material of choice. It is chosen because it is the most commonly used metal for the production of casted gully gratings. It is also readily available and relatively inexpensive and easy to cast. The material composition for the ductile iron is given below.

Table 2: Table showing ductile iron compositional analysis

SAMPLE COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS									
	%C	%Si	%S	%P	%Mn	%Cr	%Fe	%Mo	%Cu
STANDARD									
ACTUAL	3.2	2.85	0.019	0.03	0.168	-	93.7	-	-

From the material compositional analysis, the ductile iron coincides with the ASTM A536, GRADE 80-55-06. At Nigerian Foundries, the closest specification is called NFD1450/10.

Table 3: NFD1450/10 (Ductile iron) Physical, thermal and mechanical properties.

PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES	VALUE
Tensile strength, MPa	552
Yield strength, min, MPa	379
Density , g/cm ³	7.1
Melting temperature (°C)	1150 - 1200
Compressive strength, MPa	2960

THERMAL PROPERTIES	VALUE
Thermal conductivity (W/m.k)	36
Specific heat (J/kg.k)	461
Coefficient of thermal expansion (°C) ⁻¹ *10 ⁶	11.5

Advantages of Ductile iron

1. Excellent strength to weight ratio.
2. Relatively inexpensive to cast than steel.
3. Has superior machinability and can be easily casted.
4. Provides the designer with an exceptional combination of toughness, low cost manufacturing and reliability.

Table 4: Mold properties

Mold sand	Green sand, CO2 sand
Mold initial temperature	293K

Other mold material properties are listed in the appendix section of this paper.

Furnace properties

Furnace type – Induction melting furnace

Max Operating temperature - 3300°F (1800°C)

Required melting temperature - 2200°F (1200°C)

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC 15: Ductile iron Nodular structure depicted with permission from Nigerian Foundries

Material properties

Density (ρ) : Indicate the mass per unit volume of a material.

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V} \quad [\text{Kg/m}^3] \quad (3.1)$$

Density is a temperature and pressure dependent material property. In solids and liquids is just slightly affected by these factors but in gases is strongly dependent in both of them.

Thermal conductivity (k): Is the ability of a material to conduct heat. It is defined as the quantity of heat, ΔQ , transmitted during a period of time Δt through a thickness L , in a

direction normal to surface of area A, due to a temperature difference ΔT , under steady state conditions and when the heat transfer is dependent only on the temperature gradient.

$$k = \frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta t} \times \frac{L}{A \times \Delta T} \quad [\text{W/mK}] \quad (3.2)$$

Specific Heat (Cv and Cp)

In general, is the measure of the heat energy required to increase the temperature of a unit quantity of a substance by a defined temperature step. For example, how much heat must be added to increase the temperature of one gram of water by one Celsius degree. The specific heat is defined at constant pressure ([J/Kg°K]) and a constant volume ([J/m3 °K]). In gases, and have important

differences but, since for most solids and liquids and are equal, in casting processes for simplicity, we call specific heat.

$$C_p \equiv \partial H / \partial T \quad [\text{J/Kg}^\circ\text{K}] \quad (3.3)$$

Where H is the enthalpy per unit mass.

Specific Heat vs Temperature

Latent Heat (L): Is the amount of energy in the form of heat that is released or absorbed by a substance during a change of phase (solid, liquid, or gas).

$$L = \frac{Q}{m} \quad [\text{J/Kg}] \quad (3.4)$$

Where Q is the amount of energy needed to change the phase of the substance; m is the mass of the substance and L correspond to the specific latent heat of the particular substance.

Thermal diffusivity (α): Is the ratio of the thermal conductivity to the volumetric heat capacity of the material.

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{\rho c_p} \quad (3.5)$$

Where ρc_p represents the volumetric heat capacity [J/m³ K]. Mediums with high thermal diffusivity reach thermal equilibrium rapidly with their surroundings due to their capacity of fast heat transfer compared with their mass.

Elastic modulus: Elastic modulus is the ratio of stress, below the proportional limit, to the corresponding strain. It is the measure of rigidity or stiffness of a material.

$$E = \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon} = \frac{F/A}{dl/l} \quad (3.6)$$

Thermal expansion coefficient: The coefficient of thermal expansion describes how the size of an object changes with a change in temperature. Specifically, it measures the fractional change in size per degree change in temperature at a constant pressure, such that lower coefficients describe lower propensity for change in size.

$$\frac{\Delta L}{L} = \alpha_L \Delta T \quad (3.7)$$

Where

- ΔL = change in length
- L = original length
- α_L = Linear coefficient of thermal expansion
- ΔT = change in temperature

Poisson ratio: It is defined as the ratio of the change in lateral width per unit width to change in axial length per unit length caused by the axial stretching or stressing of a material.

Poisson's Ratio in XY vs Temperature

—▲— Poisson's Ratio in XY vs Temperature

318.193, 0.518908

Stress - strain

The stress- strain graph for the material is given below.

3.2 METHODS

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC
16: Method diagram

3.2 SIMULATION PROCESS

3.2.1 Process Summary

Next we present a general list of what have to be set to perform a residual stress simulation in a problem like ours. The following summary corresponds to an uncoupled thermo-mechanical analysis as described in the Introduction chapter of this work.

3.2.1.1 The Thermal simulation

- 1) Mesh the part
- 2) Define the material properties
 - a) CASTING
 - Density
 - Conductivity
 - Specific Heat
 - Latent Heat
 - Liquidus Temperature
 - Solidus Temperature
 - b) SAND MOLD
 - Density
 - Conductivity
 - Specific Heat
- 1) Define the initial boundary conditions
 - a) Initial temperature of the casting
 - b) Initial temperature of the mold
7. Define the shake-out event
 - a) By time or temperature Implementation
8. Define the interactive boundary conditions before shake-out
 - a) Conduction. Between the external surface of the casting and the surface of the mold cavity
 - b) Convection. Between the external surface of the mold and the ambient
 - c) Radiation. Between the external surface of the mold and the ambient
9. Define the interactive boundary conditions after shake-out
 - a) Convection. Between the external surface of the casting and the ambient

- b) Radiation. Between the external surface of the casting and the ambient

3.2.1.2 The Stress simulation

10. Use the same mesh used in the thermal simulation for the casting (the mold is not present in our stress analysis)
11. Define the material properties
 - a) Expansion Coefficient
 - b) Young's Modulus
 - c) Poisson's Ratio
 - d) Plasticity
 - Yield Stress
 - Plastic Strain
12. Define the initial boundary condition a. Initial temperature of the casting (as in the thermal analysis)
13. Load the nodal thermal history generated in the thermal simulation as a predefined temperature field.
14. Define the mechanical boundary conditions
 - a) Constrain the rigid body translations and rotations in X, Y and Z, but allow the body to deform.

3.3 GEOMETRY

Both initial casting geometry and optimized casting geometry have been modelled in SolidWorks 3D CAD software.

3.3.1 Isometric drawing of original casting

Figure 17: Isometric views (top) and orthographic view (bottom) of original casting

Figure 18: Isometric view of mold

3.5 MESH FOR ORIGINAL CASTING GEOMETRY

	CASTING		MOLD	
	ELEMENTS	NODES	ELEMENTS	NODES
ABAQUS	113928	27251	81935	16864

3.6 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

3.6.1 THERMAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

3.6.1.1 Before Shake-out

Conduction: Between the external surface of the casting and the surface of the mold cavity.

Convection: Between the external surface of the mold and the ambient.

Radiation: Between the external surface of the mold and the ambient.

Edit Interaction

Name: MOLD-AMBIENT -RADIATION
Type: Surface radiation
Step: before shake out (Heat transfer)

Surface: Surf-4

Radiation type: To ambient Cavity approximation (3D only)

Emissivity distribution: Uniform $f(x)$

Emissivity: 0.76

Ambient temperature: 20

Ambient temperature amplitude: (Instantaneous) $f(t)$

OK Cancel

3.6.1.2 After Shake-out

Convection: Between the external surface of the casting and the ambient. A temperature dependent convective heat transfer coefficient property was defined in Abaqus.

Radiation: Between the external surface of the casting and the ambient.

3.6.2 MECHANICAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

3.6.1.2 Stress analysis step

The task is to restrain the rigid body translations and rotations in X, Y and Z, but allow the body to deform naturally (to shrink, basically). In the cylinder model the 6 degrees of freedom has been constrained as follow:

Translations in X, Y and Z: In the flat face of the Cylinder lying in $Z=0$, a node in $Y=0$ is constrained in X, Y and Z. See Figure 4.5. Notice that in the picture, X is the horizontal axis, Y the vertical axis, and the Z axis is perpendicular to the paper.

Three rigid body translations have been constrained by fixing the point in the space. As a result the part would shrink toward the point. However, the body could still pivot in our fixed node, so now the rotations have to be constrained.

Rotations in the Y and Z axis: A node also lying in $Z=0$ and $Y=0$ but in the opposite side of the part with respect to the fixed node is constrained in Y and Z.

The constraint in Y avoids the rotation in Z and the constraint in Z avoids the rotation in Y. The reason why the node is left free to move in X is because that is the correct contraction direction toward the totally fixed node.

Rotation in the X axis: A node aligned in the Z axis with the totally fixed one (that is with the same X coordinate and $Y=0$) lying in the opposite flat face of the Cylinder is constrained in X and Y. See Figure 4.7. In this way the displacement of that node can just happen in Z, ensuring that the length axes of the body will remain parallel to the Z axis.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 COOLING CURVES FOR ORIGINAL CASTING

Figure 21: Graph of temperature against time

4.2 THERMAL COLOUR SPECTRUM FOR ORIGINAL CASTING

4.3 Stress plot for the Original Casting

Figure 23: Graph of stress at different nodes

4.4 STRESS COLOR SPECTRUM FOR ORIGINAL CASTING

Figure 25: Max principal stress results for original casting

Figure 26: Min principal stress results for original casting

4.5 ORIGINAL CASTING SIMULATION TIME

	THERMAL	STRESS	TOTAL
ABAQUS	5hrs. 18min	3hrs. 4min.	8hrs. 22min

4.6 OPTIMIZED CASTING RESULTS

The original casting's geometry is now optimized taken into account the areas of residual stress concentrations gotten from simulation results of the original casting. The new geometry and simulation results are presented below.

4.7 OPTIMIZED CASTING GEOMETRY

4.7.1 Isometric drawing of original casting

4.8 MESH FOR OPTIMIZED CASTING

	CASTING		MOLD	
	ELEMENTS	NODES	ELEMENTS	NODES
ABAQUS	112222	26844	81935	16864

x

Figure 28: Mesh isometric view of optimised casting

4.8 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The same boundary conditions still apply here that was used for the original casting geometry.

4.9 COOLING CURVE FOR OPTIMISED HUB

Figure 29: Graph of Temperature against time

4.9 THERMAL COLOUR SPECTRUM FOR ORIGINAL CASTING

4.10 STRESS PLOTS FOR THE OPTIMISED CASTING

Figure 31: Max principal stress for optimized casting

Figure 32: Min principal stress for optimized casting

Figure 33: Stress distribution at different nodes for optimized casting

4.11 STRESS COLOUR SPECTRUMS FOR THE OPTIMISED CASTING

Figure 34: Von-Mises stress results for optimized casting

Figure 35: Max principal stress results for optimized casting

Figure 36: Min principal stress results for optimized casting

4.12 COMPARISON OF ORIGINAL AND OPTIMISED CASTING RESULTS

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusions

Incorporating residual stress analysis into the casting design process can result in significant enhancements to the mechanical performance of final parts, especially with regards to fatigue life. As such, we highly recommend the utilization of numerical simulations of this nature as a routine part of casted part design. Additionally, the contrast in residual stress development between parts that have undergone topology optimization procedures and those that have not underscores the benefits of including shape optimization in the design process.

5.2 Recommendations for further research

While this study specifically focused on shape optimization for reduction of residual stresses, there could be further studies made on the reduction of residual stresses in the casting process itself.

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